

Unravelling of Natural Drugs from Asthma Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Asthma is a long-term inflammatory airway disorder that can affect many people, and numerous studies have shown that its numbers as well as severity are also increasing. Several synthetic medications like cromolyn sodium, corticosteroids, leukotriene modifiers, methylxanthine derivatives, and long-acting β 2-adrenoreceptor agonists are used to control asthmatic episodes. Mainly, the side effect-inducing factors of synthetic drugs contribute to developing a safer, potent and cost-effective drug to use judiciously for the asthma patients. There is a huge prevalence and scientific exploration of using herbal formulations as a potential remedy because herbs are an exemplary source of drugs, and herbal therapy is as ancient as mankind. This review explores the current status of natural compounds in asthma management, focusing on their pharmacological mechanisms, therapies in mitigating asthma symptoms, and their impact on patient outcomes.

Keywords: Asthma, Herbal Drug, Bronchospasm, Epidemiology.

Introduction

Millions of individuals worldwide suffer from asthma, a common obstructive lung illness characterised by persistent airway inflammation and airway hyperactivity [1]. Although asthma mortality rates are low, roughly 1% of all mortality and it is acknowledged that in many cases death could have been sidestepped with more routine care [2].

In a normal person, the airways stay relaxed for smooth airflow. During an asthma attack, airway muscles tighten (bronchospasm), walls become inflamed, and thick mucus is produced—together narrowing the airways and significantly obstructing normal breathing. These combined effects, bronchospasm, inflammation, and mucus overproduction, lead to the hallmark symptoms of asthma, including shortness of breath, wheezing, coughing and chest tightness [3].

Although asthma is typically treated as a lung-specific condition, current research

suggests that it may be a part of a systemic airway disease that affects the entire respiratory system, and this is confirmed by the circumstance that asthma often coexists with other atopic disorders, predominantly allergic rhinitis [4].

For the last three decades, bronchodilators and anti-inflammatory drugs have treated asthma, but their side effects have limited widespread use among the affected population. In several cases, cumulative attention has been paid to herbal drugs to combat chronic diseases and avoid the adverse effects caused by synthetic drugs to the patients [5]

In the USA, about 8 % of the patients are admitted to hospitals due to synthetic drug adverse effects [6]. On the contrary, in very occasional cases, reports of death are there due to herbal medication. There is no evidence of adverse reactions to herbs available even in the National Poison Control Centre databases in the United States [7]. Synthetic drugs target disease symptoms based on pathology, while herbal medicines support the body's natural healing and

overall curative process. Herbal drugs generally act mildly, control the systems and progressions that have become lacking or try to help get rid of excesses that have grown more significant [8]. Hence, it is necessary to contemplate some other beneficial options over the synthetic drugs.

In this framework, the “Drugs from Nature Targeting Inflammation (DNTI)” program is projected for the identification of different natural products possessing anti-inflammatory activity by the collective and synthetic use computational procedure, Biotechnological procedures for plants, phytochemical characterisation, ethnopharmacological acquaintance and exploration of different in-vitro as well as in vivo bioactivity models [9-11].

The purpose of this review is to explore the therapeutic potential of natural drugs, highlighting their mechanisms of action, effectiveness, and advantages over conventional treatments in the context of asthma.

Pathophysiology

Chronic inflammation is the consequence of Asthma, marked by airway inflammation, which affects smooth muscle contractibility [12]. The constraint of airflow in asthma is a persistent process leading to different characteristic changes like airway oedema, bronchoconstriction, epithelial damage, over-production of mucus, airway remodelling, and airway hyperresponsiveness [13-16] (**Figure 1**).

Atopic asthma is usually observed first in childhood or adolescence, and due to some inducing factors, wheezing starts. If there is a family history of allergic reactions, then atopic asthma also occurs [17]. Thickening of the lamina reticularis and elevation of eosinophils are the elementary variations in the airways. Increased eosinophils contain inflammatory enzymes, produce leukotrienes, and also generate a huge pro-inflammatory cytokine. Finally, it affects greater asthma severity [18]. Due to the interface of different cells and mediators with airways in airway inflammation, several pathophysiologic characteristics are

expressed, such as cough, shortness of breath and wheeze [19].

Throughout acute exacerbations, for the severe asthmatic and smoker patients, in the airways and sputum, neutrophils are increased. The actual control is not clearly known, but leukotriene B₄ may be responsible for the consequences [20, 21]. The macrophages in the airways can be stimulated by different allergens to release inflammatory mediators as well as cytokines, which intensify the inflammation [22]. It has been reported that chemokine, nitric Oxide, and immunoglobulin E are used as inflammatory mediators [23-26]. Lower Airway inflammation occasionally happens for the combination of genetic predisposition, influences of Gene-by-environment and probable modifications in the metabolite and microbiome [27]. In the majority of asthmatic patients, Type 2 inflammation is very common and it is linked with several cytokine profiles, basophils, and eosinophil-like inflammatory cells [28]. Type 2 inflammations are basically detected in allergic cases and in illnesses due to eosinophils. Via cytokines, airway epithelial cells have also been identified as a regulatory factor for type 2 inflammation [29].

Figure 1: Pathophysiology of Asthma

Common Triggering Factors

Inflammatory phases and asthma episodes can be triggered by triggers that can differ from time to time and for individuals too. In connection with these triggers, asthmatic symptoms are observed. One of the preferable points of regulating asthma is to

recognise the triggers and possibly be aware of those [30]. Common triggering factors are tobacco smoking, viral contagions in the lower or upper respiratory tract, pollution due to foreign matter, different allergens, ozone, alteration in temperature (generally cold), NSAIDs, stressed condition, exercise or excitement [31, 32].

Upper respiratory viral infections, particularly those caused by rhinovirus, are the most common triggers of asthma [33,34]. Other triggers include allergens (such as pollens, dust mites, pets, occasionally certain foods and mold spores), physical exercise, respiratory infections (like colds, sinus infections, or flu), certain medications (e.g., beta blockers), strong emotional responses (such as prolonged crying or laughing), and environmental irritants like strong odors, perfumes, or wood smoke [35-38].

Epidemiology

As of 2025, the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Global Asthma Network (GAN) estimate that around 334 million individuals globally are living with asthma [39]. The National Centre for Health Statistics reports that between 1980 and 1996, the prevalence of asthma in children under the age of 18 rose from 36 per 1,000 to 62 per 1,000 [40]. Considering the United Kingdom Scenario, asthma affects almost 5.2 million people and is responsible for 60000 hospital admissions per year [41]. The rises in asthma symptom frequency in Latin America, Africa and several regions of Asia show that the worldwide asthma load is incrementally ongoing, but the global prevalence variances are decreasing. [42].

Additionally, the frequency or prevalence can be directly influenced by the socioeconomic characteristics of specific extents, as demonstrated by the analyses of the annual difference in the prevalence of asthma [43].

Classification: Phenotype Versus Endotype

In respect of natural history, severity, and response, asthma is treated as heterogeneous.

This heterogeneity replicates the underlying mechanisms. This diversity has led to the realisation that asthma is made up of a variety of phenotypes, or recurring sets of traits [44]. The asthmatic children, three wheeze phenotypes are generally observed: (1) momentary early wheezing; (2) non-atopic wheezing; and (3) Atopic or IgE-mediated wheezing [45].

Basically, phenotypes are noticeable features that arise from a cumulative expression of environmental factors and heredity. Together, these different pathophysiologic pathways are defined by asthma endotypes at the cellular and molecular level [46].

Classifying asthma on the basis of phenotypes creates a platform for a deeper comprehension of the causation of the disease and the development of tailored strategies to combat the asthmatic condition [47].

Symptoms

Common symptoms include nighttime coughing or nocturnal cough, recurrent wheezing, shortness of breath, and chest pain, tightness, or a feeling of pressure [48,49].

Asthma is a clinical condition, and spirometry alone may not reflect its severity. Tools like the Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (AQLQ), Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ), and Asthma Control Test (ACT) help quantitatively assess symptoms during doctor visits for better evaluation. [50-52]

Diagnosis

A comprehensive medical history, family history, physical examination, symptom investigation, and objective evaluations of lung function, primarily spirometry, are taken into account for the diagnosis [53].

Broncho provocation challenge testing and evaluating for markers of airway inflammation may also be supportive for diagnosing the disease, predominantly when objective measurements of lung function are

normal in spite of the presence of asthma symptoms. [54,55]. Breathing tests, chest and sinus X-rays, blood tests and allergy tests are generally done to confirm. [56]

Management

Asthma can be controlled, not cured fully; only symptoms can be minimised. Proper asthma care will prevent symptomatic responses and hospitalisation. The drugs used for the management of asthma are listed below:

- 1.1. Anti-inflammatory: Anti-inflammatory drugs are mostly used to control asthma. This kind of drugs decreases swelling and mucus formation in the airways. Airways become less responsive to the asthmatic triggers. Corticosteroids, Mast cell stabilisers, and anti-leukotriene derivatives are mainly used as different anti-inflammatory agents in asthma. [57]
- 1.2. Bronchodilators: These drugs relax the muscle that surrounds the airways. They are recommended for short-term relief of symptoms. Mucus can be cleared by the use of bronchodilators. Beta-adrenergic agonists, anticholinergics, and methyl xanthine derivatives are mainly used as different bronchodilating agents in asthma. [58]

In different ways, these drugs can be used. Taking anti-asthma medications involves inhaling them through a nebuliser, dry powder inhaler, or metered dose inhaler. Oral medications, such as pills or liquids, may also be recommended. [59,60]

Adverse effects of Different Synthetic Drugs Currently available for Asthma

Conventional asthma treatments are often associated with various adverse effects: leukotriene modifiers may cause agitation,

aggression, hallucinations, depression, or suicidal thoughts [61]; inhaled corticosteroids can lead to delayed growth in children, adrenal suppression, bone loss, and behavioural issues [62]; theophylline is linked to convulsions, arrhythmias, tremors, and other dose-dependent side effects[63]; ipratropium may trigger acute or paradoxical bronchospasm [64]; and anticholinergics may cause dry mouth, blurred vision, palpitations, and delirium [65]. Due to these concerns, there is growing attention in the development of safer, plant-based alternatives for asthma management.

Medicinal Plants and Asthma

In both adults and children, asthma is a prevalent chronic illness with no cure. Current synthetic treatments pose long-term safety concerns, prompting ongoing research for safer, more effective alternatives suitable for prolonged use.

Traditional and natural medicines have always proved to be rich and promising sources in search of an effective remedy for asthma and other respiratory diseases. Herbs such as Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Adhatoda (*Adhatoda vasica*) and Ma-huang (*Ephedra*) have a long history of repute in this regard. In recent decades, many plants or herbs have been scientifically tested and identified for effective management of this globally chronic disease [66]. Some of the important plants with their recognised parts for the treatment of asthma have been discussed here.

Leaves

Elephantopus scaber L.

Elephantopus scaber L. (Asteraceae), found in the Western Ghats of India, is a scabrous aromatic herb and commonly known as Elephant's foot. Leaf extract (ethanol) proved to be effective antiasthmatic when tested on experimental animals. The presence of steroids, saponin, flavonoids and phenolic compounds is commonly involved in anti-asthmatic activity. It is found to decrease acetylcholine or histamine-induced bronchospasm and also protects against mast cell degranulation [67,68].

Anchomanes difformis (Blume) Engl.

Anchomanes difformis (Blume) Engl., frequently known as forest anchomanes, belongs to the Araceae family and is a large herbaceous perennial plant. In the African continent, it is treated as a native plant and grows widely in the Ivory Coast, Ghana, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Senegal, and Togo [69]. The people of Udu and Ughievwen in Delta State, Nigeria, used this plant to treat asthma as traditional medicine. Later, the aqueous leaf extract was found to possess anti-asthmatic properties by reducing histamine-induced bronchospasm, fluid volume, and tracheal fluid viscosity in guinea pigs as experimental animals. [70]

Cassia sophera L.

Cassia sophera L. (Caesalpiniaceae) is traditionally used to treat asthma and bronchitis. The ethanolic extract of leaves was scientifically proven to have antiasthmatic activity in clonidine, haloperidol-induced catalepsy and histamine-induced bronchoconstriction in animal models [71].

Piper betel Blanco

Piper betel Blanco has been traditionally used to cure different airway problems such as cold, cough and asthma. In the guinea pig, aqueous and ethanol extracts of leaves demonstrated anti-asthmatic action by reducing histamine-induced bronchoconstriction [72].

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb.

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb. belongs to the Simaroubaceae and is conventionally used in the Indian system of medicine as a bronchodilator in the treatment of asthma and cough. Methanolic leaf extract of *A. excelsa* was investigated as an effective one in treating asthma when assessed experimentally using different *in vivo* and *in vitro* models such as Clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice, mast cells degranulation in rat and goat tracheal chain preparation and milk-induced leukocytosis. [73]

Ageratum conyzoides (L.) L.

The tall, herbaceous annual plant *Ageratum*

conyzoides (L.) L., a member of the Asteraceae family, is indigenous to tropical America and is found across tropical and subtropical regions worldwide. Antihistaminic activity of hydroalcoholic extract of leaves is scientifically demonstrated, which acts by inhibiting catalepsy induced by clonidine in mice. [74]

Physalis angulata L.

Physalis angulata L., belonging to the family Solanaceae, is also known as winter cherry or wild tomato. In India, it is used in the treatment of asthma in some states. The management of asthma has been demonstrated to benefit from the usage of methanolic leaf extract by showing anti-histaminic property using guinea pig ileum and trachea preparations and rat fundus strip [75]. The effect of this extract on cyclic GMP and histamine through the H1 receptor is suggested as a possible mechanism of anti-asthmatic activity.

Aerial Parts

Aerva lanta (L.) Juss.

Aerva lanta (L.) Juss. (Amaranthaceae) It is an erect herbaceous weed and commonly found in the warmer regions of India in the lowlands. Ethanol extract of aerial parts showed antiasthmatic activity when tested in clonidine-induced catalepsy, mast cell degranulation in mice and the isolated goat tracheal chain preparation model [76]. The antiasthmatic activity of *A. lanata* has been associated with the suppression of oedema, IgE antibodies, pro-inflammatory cytokines, and elevation of aquaporin levels in experimental models.

Euphorbia hirta L.

Euphorbia hirta L. (Euphorbiaceae), popularly known as asthma weed, is a wild herbaceous plant. The entire aerial portion of the plant's ethanol extract exhibited antiallergic and antihistaminic properties in experimental animals by preventing the passive cutaneous anaphylaxis and paw anaphylaxis reaction. Additionally, the extract prevents mast cells from degranulating [77].

Phymatodes scolopendria (Burm.) Ching

Phymatodes scolopendria (Burm.) Ching is a common pteridophyte that belongs to the family Polypodiaceae and is commonly grown on the east coast of Madagascar as a crawling fern. The coumarin and 1, 2-benzopyrone isolated from the ethanol extract of aerial parts displayed promising bronchodilator activity by preventing histamine or carbachol-induced pre-contracted trachea of the guinea pig [78]. It inhibited the external calcium spasm effect in a non-competitive manner and modified the broncho-constructor activity of KCl.

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers.

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers. is a common perennial grass which occurs throughout India. Extracts of the whole plant using different solvents like methanol, hexane, and acetone showed promising effects against asthma when tested in different models such as mast cell degranulation and anaphylaxis [79].

Euphorbia thymifolia L.

Euphorbia thymifolia L. (Euphorbiaceae) is a common annual herb found throughout the tropical and subtropical regions of India. The plant is small, branched and hispidly pubescent [80]. Quercitrin (3-rhamnosylquercetin) is commonly found in *E. hirta* as a bioflavonoid, which is converted into quercetin in the alimentary canal, causing prominent anti-inflammatory and anti-asthmatic effects. Different sterols like β -sitosterol, 1-hexacosanol, euphorbolhexacozone, tinaloxin, stigmasterol, and campesterol isolated from *E. hirta* showed strong anti-inflammatory and anti-asthmatic effects that were dose-dependent [81]. The aerial parts of the plant showed promising mast cell stabilising activity when tested on intestinal mesenteric mast cells produced by compound 48/80 and anti-asthmatic activity by reducing bronchospasm induced by histamine in experimental animals [82].

Bark, Stem and Wood

Casuarina equisetifolia L.

Casuarina equisetifolia L. (Casuarinaceae) is

an evergreen tree and is cultivated in different parts of India. The methanolic extract of bark and wood showed the ability to inhibit the contraction of trachea induced by histamine, degranulation of mast cells, and catalepsy induced by clonidine in experimental animals, thereby exhibiting promising antihistaminic activity [83].

Ficus benghalensis L.

Ficus benghalensis L. belongs to the family Moraceae and is commonly grown as a big tree throughout the tropical regions of India. Antihistaminic activity is shown by the bark when extracted using solvents like ethyl acetate, ethanol or water by inhibiting catalepsy induced by clonidine in mice [84,85].

Amburana cearensis (Allemão) A.C.Sm.

It is a common medicinal plant of northeastern Brazil (savannah) and belongs to the family Fabaceae. It is popular in combating asthma and other respiratory disorders. A flavonoid called isokaempferide, which was extracted from trunk barks, demonstrated a notable reduction in contraction when KCl was applied to the trachea of guinea pigs [86].

Myrica esculenta Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don

It is a common perennial shrub that belongs to the family Myricaceae. In the Ayurvedic system of medicine, it is effective in treating bronchitis and asthma. Stem bark shows bronchodilator activity by inhibiting bronchospasm induced by acetylcholine, antianaphylactic activity by inhibiting egg albumin-induced anaphylaxis and by relaxing acetylcholine and histamine-induced contraction using the guinea pig as experimental animal. [87].

Conclusion

Asthma is a chronic disease and is becoming a challenging issue for the current generation in all age groups. Many synthetic drugs are available for asthma management, but their safety in long-term use is always questionable. Scientists from all over the world are always working to find effective and safe drugs for long-term use in asthma.

Medicinal plants have been at the forefront of this research since antiquity. A large number of research works on experimental animal models have been carried out in this direction, which show promising results. However, the lack of studies on pharmacokinetic properties and safety profile

is a matter of concern in anti-asthmatic activity. Further investigations addressing these limitations and identification, isolation, and characterisation of bioactive molecules from plant sources may lead to effective and safe therapy of asthma, which may be economically viable for mankind.

Table 1: List of plants having anti-asthmatic properties

Plant	Family	Part	Chemical Constituents	Mechanism of action	Reference
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	Leaves	Alkaloids	Bronchodilator	[88]
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R. Br.	Apocynaceae	Leaves	Ditamine, Echitamine, and Echitenines	Bronchodilator	[89]
<i>Belamcanda chinensis</i> (L.) DC.	Iridaceae	Leaves	Tectorigenin	Bronchodilator	[90]
<i>Cissampelos sympodialis</i> Eichler	Menispermaceae	Leaves	Warifteine, α -bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloid	Bronchodilator	[91-93]
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> L.	Ginkgoaceae	Leaves	Ginkgolides	Bronchodilator	[94]
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Myrcenol, Nerol, Eugenol	Bronchodilator	[95]
<i>Tylophora indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr.	Apocynaceae	Leaves	Tylophorine	Bronchodilator	[96]
<i>Artemisia caerulescens</i> L.	Asteraceae	Aerial parts	Quercetin, isorhamnetin	Bronchodilator	[97]
<i>Galphimia glauca</i> Cav.	Malpighiaceae	Aerial parts	Tetragalloylquinic acid, Quercetin	Bronchodilator	[98]
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae	Aerial parts	Flavonoids, Tephrosin	Bronchodilator	[99]
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.	Meliaceae	Leaves	Nimbin, nimbinine, Nimbandiol, quercetin	Mast cell stabilisers	[100]
<i>Cassia alata</i> L.	Fabaceae	Leaves	Anthraquinones, Flavonoids	Mast cell stabilisers	[101]
<i>Crinum glaucum</i> A.Chev.	Amaryllidaceae	Leaves	Alkaloids, lycorine, crinamine	Mast cell stabilisers	[102]
<i>Tylophora asthmatica</i> (L. f.) Wight & Arn.	Apocynaceae	Leaves	Tylophorine	Mast cell stabilisers	[103]
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Aerial parts	Oleanolic acid	Mast cell stabilisers	[104]
<i>Bidens parviflora</i> Willd.	Asteraceae	Aerial parts	Glycosides	Mast cell stabilisers	[105]
<i>Striga orobanchoides</i>	Orobanchaceae	Aerial	Flavonoids	Mast cell	[106]

(R. Br.) Benth.		parts		stabilisers	
<i>Aquilaria agallocha</i> Roxb.	Thymelaeaceae	Stem	Triterpenoids	Mast cell stabilisers	[107]
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers	Menispermaceae	Stem	Tinosporin	Mast cell stabilisers	[95]
<i>Coleus forskohlii</i> (Willd.) Briq.	Lamiaceae	Roots	Forskolin (diterpenoid)	Mast cell stabilisers	[108]
<i>Inula racemosa</i> Hook.f.	Asteraceae	Roots	Inulolide	Mast cell stabilisers	[109]
<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L.) Kuntze	Theaceae	Leaves	Flavonoids	Anti allergics	[110]
<i>Hydrangea macrophylla</i> (Thunb.) Ser.	Hydrangeaceae	Leaves	Glycosides	Anti allergics	[111]
<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Casticin, isoorientin, Chrysophenol D, Luteolin	Anti allergics	[112]
<i>Asiasarum sieboldii</i> (Miq.) F.Maek.	Aristolochiaceae	Roots	Asarinin, Elemicin, Methyleugenol, asarone	Anti allergics	[113]
<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Rhizomes	Curcumin and tetrahydrocurcumin	Anti allergics	[110]
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	Rutaceae	Leaves	Aegelin, Aegelemine, Aegeline	Anti-spasmodic/ Spasmolytics	[114]
<i>Pavetta crassipes</i> K.Schum.	Rubiaceae	Leaves	Flavonoids, tannins, anthraquinones	Anti-spasmodic/ Spasmolytics	[115]
<i>Drymis winteri</i> J.R. Forst. & G.Forst.	Winteraceae	Bark	Terpenes	Anti-spasmodic/ Spasmolytics	[116]
<i>Ferula sinaica</i> Boiss.	Apiaceae	Root	Resins	Anti-spasmodic/ Spasmolytics	[117]
<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Seeds	Thymoquinone	Leukotriene biosynthesis inhibitors	[118]
<i>Magnolia obovata</i> Thunb.	Magnoliaceae	Stem bark	Magnolol and honokiol	Cyclooxygenase inhibitor	[119]
<i>Crataegus pinnatifida</i> Bunge	Rosaceae	Fruit	Flavanoids	Cyclooxygenase inhibitor	[120]
<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb. ex Colebr.	Burseraceae	Gum resin	Boswellic acid	Lipoxygenase inhibitors	[121]
<i>Proustia pyrifolia</i> DC.	Asteraceae	Whole plant	B-sitosterol, quercetin and dihydroquercetin	Lipoxygenase inhibitors	[122]

<i>Nidularium procerum</i> Lindm.	Bromeliaceae	Leaves	Flavonoids, Steroids	Interleukins (ILs) biosynthesis inhibitors	[123]
<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i> (Pursh) Nutt.	Berberidaceae	Stem bark	Protoberberin e, Berbamine, Tetrandrine	Interleukins (ILs) biosynthesis inhibitors	[124]
<i>Galphimia glauca</i> Cav.	Malpighiaceae	Aerial	Tetragalloylq uinic acid, Quercetin	Platelet- activating factor (PAF) inhibitors	[125]

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